

A Critical Exploration of The Link Between Child Abuse, Faith & Belief.

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Abstract

This research project investigates the phenomenon of child abuse and its links to faith or belief in the UK context. This report focuses on this form of abuse because the main victims are often uniquely vulnerable: they are children with learning disabilities. Also, based on the most recent Children in Need Census 2017-2018, there is an increase of 11% in child abuse linked to faith or belief compared to 2016-2017 (vcf-uk.org, 2024). Therefore, research on this topic is essential given the limited quantity of data available about child abuse linked to faith or belief. Moreover, the researcher is uniquely motivated to investigate this issue, being a support worker for children with learning disabilities. This research is a desk-based review of previous data collected by other researchers; this includes the work of Eleonor Stobart (2006) and Jean La Fontaine (2009), in combination with London Metropolitan Police data. The key result of this study is that while the UK government and London Metropolitan Police recognise abuse linked to faith or belief as a serious offence, this phenomenon (the link between child abuse and faith/belief) is under-researched. More research is needed in this area to understand the scale and impact of the relationship between child abuse and faith/belief.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

This paper is an attempt to investigate in depth the child abuse linked to faith or belief, often referred to as “faith-based abuse” here in the UK (KSCP, 2024). In addition, child abuse linked to faith or belief can incorporate beliefs of witchcraft and spirit possession hence considering the possibility that a/the devil or demon can possess a child (Safeguarding Network, 2024). Several cases can be used as examples of child abuse linked to faith or belief (CALFB) definition given by Clark et al. (2023) here in the UK, like the eight-years-old Victoria Climbié killed in 2005, or ‘Adam’ the Nigerian child whose headless torso was found on the Thames in 2001 who the police believe was murdered following a ritual killing as his limbs were removed, Child B who was victim of abuse in 2005, and Samira Ullah killed by her father in 2004 because she was accused of being possessed by a jinn in East London (La Fontaine, 2009). Brierley (2001) estimated there were 4,467 Pentecostal congregations in Britain in 2000. The estimates revealed that in 1995 there were over three thousand churches with over 300,000 members in the UK between the African and Caribbean Evangelical Alliance (Brierley, 2001). The ‘professional exorcist’ Revd Kevin Logan in 1986 was an Anglican vicar of the Lancashire parish of St Johns, near Blackburn (Jenkins, 1995). Revd Kevin Logan claimed that over 80% of children are in some ways affected by occult forces. Also, Revd Kevin Logan has written nine books warning about the power of paganism and the occult as it is a danger to society trying to reinforce the idea that the practice of exorcism is a good practice in the Anglican church (Live 2008). Moreover, in 2006 Angus Stickler in his documentary called *The Newsnight Documentary* exposed the work of the Congolese pastor Dieudonne Tukala of the Tottenham Church in North London, who allegedly was diagnosing children to be possessed by evil spirits and suggesting to their families to send them back in Africa to be exorcised (van Eck Duymaer van Twist, 2009). Pastor Tukala was later accused and arrested on suspicion of inciting child cruelty but was not sentenced because of a lack of evidence (Davies, 2006). Nzuzi Mayingi, killed himself after the pastor accused his wife and their unborn child of being a witch. Nzuzi Mayingi because of his deep belief in witchcraft, and following the accusation made by Dr. Tukala, beat his wife and kicked her out of the house, then committed suicide after only 18 months in the UK (Davies, 2006). According to the Victoria Climbié Foundation UK, the latest data on child abuse cases linked to faith or belief (CALFB) show that there has been an increase from 1,460 mentions in safeguarding assessments recorded for 2016-17, to 1,630 in the most recent Children in Need Census 2017-18. Since 2004, VCF has been empowering practitioners, through independent advocacy, assessments, or case reviews, to identify and appropriately respond to issues of child abuse linked to faith or belief, within their wider safeguarding processes (vcf-uk.org. 2024).

In October 2023 the researcher (I, hereafter) started working for a charity company called LDN London, which works in collaboration with vulnerable people affected by learning disabilities. I attended different mandatory training sessions to help me understand the various necessities of the people whom I support. Additionally, I come from a traditional Italian-catholic background. In combination with my study in criminology and psychology, I started to critically reflect on how religions can influence populations and have a strong impact on commonly shared beliefs even when it comes to approaching vulnerable children with learning disabilities.

Csordas (2017) highlighted the social and cultural significance of this phenomenon as a key concept of research (Csordas, 2017). Following Csordas (2017) there has been a resurgence of exorcism as a practice in the Catholic Church starting from the early 21st century. Exorcism is a religious/spiritual ritual, performed by specialist priests, following the clear consent of the bishop in charge, in combination with the authorization of the jurisdiction in an area where the exorcism is taking place. The practice of exorcism could be considered as an alternative to traditional and modern therapies, a way to protect the perceived victim of possession by sending away the perceived evil spirit from their body and saving their perceived soul. From this faith/belief-based view, exorcism is a practice which is both therapeutic and cosmological (Csordas, 2017).

The Metropolitan Police (2023) define abuse as linked to faith or belief when a child is the victim of a harmful practice or ritual connected to faiths or belief in witchcraft, spirit, or demonic possession, and might have ritual or satanic abuse features (Metropolitan Police, 2023). Based on the definition given by the Department of Education in 2012, child abuse is linked to faith or belief when that belief in witchcraft, spirit possession, and other forms of the supernatural can lead to children being blamed for unfortunate 'bad luck' events. The fear of the unnatural is also known to be used to make children more comply with being trafficked for domestic slavery and sexual exploitation (GOV.UK, 2012). Metropolitan Police (2023) explains that this abuse can take place for varied reasons, and ritualistic abuse can prolong sexual, physical, and psychological harm (Metropolitan Police, 2023). Safeguarding Network (2024) an association created appositely to tackle abuse linked to faith or belief explained through the research conducted about this topic that child "faith-based abuse" can imply beating, burning, cutting/stubbing, and semi-strangling the victim who most of the time has been restrained. The Social Care Institute for Excellence (SCIE), a non-profit independent social care charity indicated physical abuse, sexual abuse, neglect, and emotional abuse as the four main types of abuse also linked to faith or beliefs that might have a profound impact on children's long-term development and wellbeing (SCIE, 2020).

In the UK, different important examples of child abuse linked to faith or belief (CALFB) (Clarck et al., 2023), involve vulnerable victims as children, specifically those with learning disabilities like Kristi Bamu, who was killed by his sister and her boyfriend on Christmas day in 2010 (The Guardian, 2012). The research conducted in 2023 by Kirklees Safeguarding Children Partnership (KSCP) on cases of children abused that could be linked to faith or belief indicated that the most common age for children to be abused is between the ages of 2 and 14 years (KSCP, 2024). These cases of abuse linked to faith or belief are mainly reported by schools and other non-governmental organizations; often the abuse is reported when the situation has escalated (KSCP, 2024). Moreover, recent national data pointed out that 28% of children victims of abuse were under the age of 2 years old, 17% were between the ages of 3 and 5, 25% were between 6 and 10, 19% were between 11 and 14, and the 10% were 15 and older (Guastafarro & Shipe, 2024).

A national action plan was launched in August 2012 to provide a template for all the local authorities to follow to tackle faith-based abuse. However, the research conducted by the Victoria Climbié Foundation UK in 2016 showed that only 12% of respondents were familiar with the National Action Plan and 77% of respondents did not have any knowledge whatsoever of their Local Safeguarding Children Board (LSCB). This included a policy on this form of abuse (vcf-uk.org, 2024). Moreover, recent data collected by the Victoria Climbié Foundation UK on child abuse showed that there is an increase in cases from 1,460 mentions in the safeguarding assessment recorded for 2016-2017 to 1,630 in the most recent report Children in Needs Census 2017-18. Also, the Census pointed out that there is an 11% increase in cases of child abuse linked to faith or belief (vcf-uk.org, 2024).

Of course, not all child abuse is faith-based, although there is a huge percentage of abuse perpetrated by religious figures who are abusing their power. The Metropolitan Police (2024) highlighted the fact that it is under-reported and could be perpetrated for different reasons as an important aspect of this type of abuse. The Catholic religion is often associated with scandals of religious figures who can use their power and the influence connected to the religion to sexually abuse vulnerable children. The Independent Inquiry into child sexual abuse (IICSA) published its final Report in October 2022. The report is an examination of the extent of institutional failings by the Roman Catholic Church in England and Wales to protect children from sexual abuse and reviewed the current safeguarding regime adopted by the Church in the UK. In fact, between 1970 and 2015, the Roman Catholic Church received more than 900 complaints involving over 3,000 instances of child sexual abuse involving priests, monks, and volunteers. During this period, there were 177 prosecutions resulting in 133 convictions. Moreover, civil claims against the dioceses and religious institutes led to millions of pounds destined for

compensation (iicsa.org.uk, 2024). Additionally, based on the independent inquiry on child sexual abuse (IICSA), there have been more than 100 reported allegations each year since 2016 across the entire period of nearly 50 years covered by this Inquiry; the true scale of sexual abuse of children is likely to have been much higher (iicsa.org.uk, 2024).

Based on Stobart (2009), the most vulnerable victims of this abuse are children with learning disabilities, mental issues, and behavioural issues (Stobart, 2009). Based on Franklin (2019) the data show that disabled children are 3.8 times more likely to be neglected or physically abused, 3.1 times more likely to be sexually abused, and 3.9 times more likely to be emotionally abused. Moreover, findings show that 31% of disabled children can suffer from abuse compared to 9% of the non-disabled children population. Disabled children are also at a higher risk of experiencing multiple abuses and enduring numerous episodes of abuse (Franklin, 2019). Furthermore, working in the sector with learning disabilities can give an insight into this delicate and important topic that is not taken into consideration during the training, to learn how to deal with vulnerable people and children. It is important to investigate and reflect on the ability of social services and key workers to tackle CALFB to prevent this crime, indeed when vulnerable people are living permanently in services. Additionally, further improvement in training the people who work with vulnerable children could be a very effective response to this crime. Therefore, the support provided by associations like Safeguarding Network, established in 2017 by John Woodhouse and Andrew Martin (both social workers), is playing a significant role in training other charities and associations to tackle CALFB (Safeguarding.Network, 2024).

The organization I work for did not provide training in association with Safeguarding Network, therefore I felt the necessity to understand more about the reasons why social workers like me are not trained to tackle CALFB. One of the main critiques that is possible to make is the lack of information about this crime. Moreover, based on Dutt and Phillips (2000) the lack of knowledge about different cultures within minority communities can be considered as an important obstacle to understanding what is going on in specific situations that involve children. The lack of understanding can be an issue as this is not a phenomenon extended to an entire community but only in restricted cases inside the different communities (Dutt and Phillips, 2000). A good example could be the case of Samira Ullah who was killed by her father, a drug addict who struggled with mental issues that led him to believe that an evil spirit was inside the body of Samira. Therefore, key figures and their studies like Littlewood (2004) are fundamental to investigating CALFB. Littlewood (2004) suggests that understanding different cultures and belief systems is essential to improve the safeguarding of children as criminalizing what is

different and not understood properly only makes people more afraid of institutions and consequently leads to more abuses of this nature going unnoticed until it's too late (Littlewood, 2004). The Metropolitan Police (2024) data confirms this, as CALFB is a very under-reported crime (Metropolitan Police, 2024).

This project will try to review the data about CALFB to make more information available to support workers and whoever is interested in the topic; my dissertation will try to research why issues like the lack of specific training and available data are not being addressed as a serious matter. This is an effort to provide a recommendation based on the direct experience of support workers to improve the safeguarding of children from any culture and background. Therefore, the next chapter; a review of the literature used during this research, will help to understand the importance of investigating such an under-researched form of abuse still going on here in the UK. The research questions that have guided this work are as follows:

1. How do religious beliefs and practices influence the reporting and recognition of child abuse within faith communities?
2. What role do religious leaders and institutions play in either perpetuating or preventing of child abuse?
3. How does religious or spiritual trauma manifest in victims of child abuse within religious settings?

Chapter 2: The London Context of CALFB

As stated previously, belief in evil forces that can possess children and bring misfortune to the family is part of a range of diverse faith/belief-oriented cultures (La Fontaine, 2009). Simon Dein et al. (2008) conducted between 2004 and 2005 an ethnographic fieldwork among the Bangladeshi community established in East London and the common belief in negative and positive spirits like jinn, in the use of black magic, sorcery, and the evil eye. For these communities, these perceived invisible forces explain the many misfortunes or prosperity that characterized the Bangladeshi community (Dein et al., 2008).

A semi-structured interview study conducted by Dein et al (2008) investigated the understanding of mental illness among 30 Bangladeshi mental health service users and their families attending a day centre in Tower Hamlets, East London. The service users have all received support because of their mental health issues which include different conditions like schizophrenia, depression, bipolar disorder, and anxiety. The families held jinn responsible for their illness and pointed out the efficacy of the Qur'an in coping with their pathologies (Dein et al., 2008). The belief in jinn is still prevalent in the Bangladeshi community, it might influence in specific ways the approach of the community to the concept of health and may impede children from getting the essential help that they might require. However, beliefs about evil spirits possessing children are less common among the modern generation nowadays as the new generation is more educated and aware of abuse in general compared to the oldest generation (Dein et al., 2008).

The UK Government in 2023 published the National Action Plan created to tackle specifically abuse to children connected to faith or belief (GOV.UK, 2023). The National Action Plan (2023) is the product of the collaboration between the central government, religious leaders, and voluntary subdivision organizations with the Metropolitan Police, and compared to the one from 2012 highlighted how it is fundamental to improve citizen's knowledge about children accused of practice witchcraft (GOV.UK, 2023). Hall (2016) emphasized how Article 9: Freedom of thought, conscience, and religion of the European Convention on Human Rights (EHRC, 2021) guarantees the freedom to practice any belief or faith. Also, Article 9.2 stated that the freedom to manifest any religion or belief should be only subject to specific limitations established by the law as necessary in a democratic society in the interests of public safety and order, health and morals, for the protection of others' rights and freedom (EHRC, 2021).

The Metropolitan Police's statistics data from 2023, pointed out that the number of cases involving children abused in connection with religious belief is small (Met Police, 2023) compared to a total of 30,700 cases of children who were placed under the child protection registers in England (La Fontaine, 2009). In the UK, 0.5% of infants end up in child protection every year and 5%-15% of children report occurrences of ill-treatment at a certain point during their infancy (Degli Esposti, Taylor, Humphreys, & Bowes, 2018; May-Chahal & Cawson, 2005). The figures provided by the Government updated in 2023 stated that 50, 780 children are on protection plans, statistically 0.3% down since 2022 (Gov. UK, 2024). An infant who is a victim of maltreatment can be affected by major negative outcomes like Post Traumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD), anxiety, and depression (Kisely et al., 2020). Moreover, child maltreatment is associated with extreme antisocial behaviour with a constant and stable correlation remaining up to the age of 50 (Kisely et al., 2020). Research also suggests the worth of granting long-term support for the victims who experience child mistreatment as it has been considered a major public health problem (Degli Esposti et al., 2020).

To cope with the traumatic experience is often hard for a child (Met Police, 2023). Moreover, the data and the details of the cases of abuse that involved under-age vulnerable people linked to religious reasons are not recorded systematically; this is an important limitation not only for those who aim to research this phenomenon but also for the Metropolitan Police and other key figures like social workers and support workers as they are not properly trained and have a lack of clear safeguarding protocols (New Humanist, 2012).

One of the most recent cases of abuse linked to faith or belief happened in Stratford (London) in 2012. The victim, Kristy Bamu, was a 15-year-old teenager who was repeatedly tortured, beaten, and mutilated for different days before being killed by his sister and her boyfriend. The couple stated during the trial that they were sure that Kristy was a witch. Kristy was vulnerable and had learning disabilities (BBC, 2012). The Victoria Climbié Foundation and the Metropolitan Police worked together during Kristy Bamu's investigation (GOV.UK 2023). Also, the Victoria Climbié Foundation is focusing on tackling abuse linked to faith and belief to honour the memory of Victoria Climbié murdered in London in early 2000 by her great-aunt and her partner (vfc.-uk.org, 2024). They both believed that Victoria was a witch (New Humanist 2012).

Eleonor Stobart's (2009) review of different cases investigated by the Metropolitan Police (Simon et al., 2012). Stobart's (2009) review analysed a total of thirty-eight child abuse cases (involving forty-seven kids) accused of 'witchcraft' or 'possession'. These cases were mostly from London (specifically 32 of 38 cases) the rest were from other parts of the UK (Simon et al., 2012). Following Stobart (2009), the

issues related to witchcraft and spirit possession were more likely to happen in complex family structures, large family households, or within new migrant groups (Stobart, 2009). Additionally, these children are often victims of distant relatives and used as scapegoats for family problems. Moreover, neglect and beating are the two most ordinary methods of abuse operated by the abusers (Stobart, 2009). Furthermore, Jean La Fontaine (2009) in her book *The Devil's Children: Spirit Possession to Witchcraft: New Allegations that Affect Children* pointed out that abuse that involves the use of 'satanic rituals' is often family-related; most common victims are usually teenagers instead of young children. Moreover, Simon et al. (2012), explained that the typology of abuse differs by gender, for instance, males are more associated with paedophile networks compared to girls who are more victims of domestic sexual abuse, and male young children and teenagers are more targeted. A common feature regarding girls' victims of abuse linked to faith or belief is the noticeable age of the victims (Simon et al., 2012).

The Department of Education (DfE) in 2006 commissioned the Childhood Wellbeing Research Centre (CWRC) in collaboration with Eleonor Stobart to oversee a small-scale review of earlier studies conducted on cases of abuse linked to faith or beliefs (Simon et al., 2012). Hence, CWRC reviewed thirty-eight child abuse cases involving forty-seven children that happened between 2000 and 2005. The children involved in the cases of abuse reviewed by CWRC were from diverse backgrounds including African, South Asian, and European (Simon et al., 2012). Nevertheless, following the UK Government (2023) there is another important aspect to take into consideration which is the indoctrination of the fears of magic and witchcraft in children to make them more compliant when, for example, they are being trafficked for domestic slavery or being victims of sexual exploitations (GOV.UK 2023).

Chapter 3: The Stobart Report, Possession & Mental health issues

3.1 The Stobart Report

Eleonor Stobart conducted a research report for the Department of Education and Skills (DfES) in 2006 about 'Child Abuse Linked to Accusation of "Possession" and "Witchcraft"' in 2006 (La Fontaine, 2009). The report is a desk-based investigation and discussion with social workers, schoolteachers, the Metropolitan police, voluntary workers, and others who know the issue. Stobart (2006) has been collecting and investigating cases that ensued in the UK since January 2000. The data collected were often limited, although this investigation led Stobart to the conclusion that the belief in 'witchcraft' and 'possession' is quite extensive. Stobart (2006) was able to identify seventy-four cases of abuse connected to accusations of 'witchcraft' and 'possession'. However, only cases with common identifying factors were analysed to avoid double-counting. Hence, the report conducted by Stobart includes only thirty-eight of these cases. However, fourteen cases were detected before the inquiry, and new cases were reported before the report was published (Stobart, 2006).

Some of the analyses by Eleonor Stobart (2006) have occurred in the London area, specifically in East London in boroughs like Hackney and Tower Hamlets. Nevertheless, this is not considered specifically as a London problem as twenty-four new cases have emerged while Stobart (2006) was researching the phenomenon of child abuse linked to faith or belief (CALFB) (La Fontaine, 2009). It is also quite complicated to establish the nationality and background of both parents/careers and the victims. Yet, between the thirty-seven cases analysed there was a prevalence of a significant cluster coming from the Democratic Republic of Congo. Another important factor is the period of UK residency as accusations of witchcraft were more common among new immigrant communities who struggled to integrate themselves into such unfamiliar cultural backgrounds (La Fontaine, 2009). Stobart's report (2006) also, pointed out that half of the children's victims of CALFB were born in the UK with an age range of 2-14 years, although six cases were between 8-14 years old (Stobart, 2006).

Regarding the religion of the victims, Stobart's report (2006) established that the families involved described themselves as Christians. However, researching this factor is difficult as most of the time, religion is not recorded in the case notes. Hence, it is not viable to assess the role of the religions when it comes to talking about CALFB. Furthermore, all the cases of abuse associated with religions different from Christianity were discovered during the fourth month of this research, hence the emphasis has

been directed specifically on some communities, and gathering more information could lead to individualized cases across other religions (Stobart, 2006). Moreover, the connection between the primary caregiver and the place of worship is an important aspect to take into consideration, as the religious leader can influence the carer and provide a diagnosis of demonic possession. Also, another recurrent element is the unclear family structure, as Stobart's report (2006) pointed out that in six cases of abuse, the child was living with their natural parents while in 19 cases, between the 38 investigated, a carer (most of the time a distant relative) oversaw the child (La Fontaine, 2009). The Victoria Climbié Foundation UK (2024) welcomes data released by the Department for Education, in November 2017. The Children in Need Census (2017) includes a new category for child abuse linked to faith or belief (CALFB). Initial indications show 1,460 cases across England. Additionally, Mor Dioum, VCF Director and former Chair of the National Working Group on Child Abuse Linked to Faith or Belief, insists on the importance of raising awareness about this abuse (vcf-uk.org.,2024).

3.2 Learning Disabilities, Children & Diverse Types of Abuse

Stobart's report (2006) found another important common feature between the cases of CALFB analysed. The majority of the child victims of abuse linked to faith or belief had some form of disability or learning disabilities, challenging behaviour, sleepwalking, wetting the bed, and nightmares between twenty-two cases investigated. Children with disabilities have been seen as 'different.' Stobart's report (2006) identified fourteen cases between the cases investigated, which used to have various levels of disabilities, from mild to severe. The recurrent disabilities were epilepsy (2 cases), stammer (2 cases), deafness (1 case), learning disabilities (4 cases), autism (2 cases), mental health issues (4 cases), and life-limiting illness (2 cases). Hence, because the abuse is often more common in cases where children are under the care of external components of the family, it is possible to say that it is more likely that the carer to see disabilities, physical and non, as demonic possessions compared to the biological parents of the children's victims of CALFB (Stobart, 2006).

Stobart's report (2006) defined the different types of abuse perpetrated on children accused of being witches like beating, burning, cutting/stabbing, making children fast or starving them, likewise isolating them. For example, in one of the cases, the primary caregivers were so afraid of the infant that they would only touch him with a long stick. In another case that Stobart investigated, five children were taken away from school to detach them further. However, neglect is the most recurrent type of abuse as in nineteen cases the stage of neglect was depicted as severe (Stobart, 2006). Also, Gonzalez et al., (2024) established that neglect can include inadequate health care, education, supervision, shelter, protection from hazardous situations or environments, and basic needs such as food and clothing. The

common element with the abuse linked to faith or belief is that neglect can also involve physical abuse that may include beating, shaking, burning, and biting (Gonzalez et al., 2024).

Stobart's report (2006) indicated that the main causes of these abuses are related to faith or belief, elements like the struggle of these families to integrate with the socio-cultural environment; the fear that their children could be corrupted by the different lifestyle and hence begin to distance themselves from important values like family and religion (Stobart, 2006). Douglas (1995) explained how these children are often considered the 'scapegoats' for the families who host them. These children are considered 'vulnerable' and 'outsiders,' easy figures to blame for all the misfortune and socio-economic issues of the families who committed the abuses (Douglas, 1995). Besides, scapegoating is considered by Strepp (2023) a form of parental verbal abuse that allows the parents to minimize the responsibility and explain negative events, enhancing a sense of control, usually, the scapegoat role can target one child. Also, the parent can maintain control over the interactions and behaviours of family members and the family narrative (Strepp, 2023). In addition, Strepp (2023) pointed out that there is little research about how a target gets chosen, but it is a recurrent factor that the child most considered a rebel is often the chosen one. Moreover, because bullying and scapegoating have similar intentions as both give the abuser a sense of power, another common element is selecting the child who tends to react most to challenging situations or is accused of being "too sensitive" and hence easy to attack (Strepp, 2023).

3.3 Possession & Mental Health Issues

Roland Littlewood (2004) defines possession as a 'trance state' which has two distinct aspects; the first one is the acceptance of the possession (the person is aware of the possession), and an altered state of consciousness (Littlewood, 2004). Also, Lewis (1996) explained that 'sought possession' is both socially based on the society's religious culture, (mostly male) and the peripheral cults (more marginal and female). However, this distinction is more helpful to anthropologists than clinicians (Lewis, 1996).

All these prerogatives are very similar to the catholic religious practice of exorcism. The United States Conference of Catholic Bishops defines exorcism as a specific form of prayer that the Church uses against the power of the Devil. However, the exorcist must follow the "utmost circumspection and prudence" before proceeding to the rite. As part of the evaluation process (which can be established in a diocesan protocol), the person indicated as possessed should avail himself/herself of a thorough medical and psychological/psychiatric evaluation (usccb.org.,2024). Littlewood (2004) provides an example of the involuntary possession of an infant using a case study: A 45-year-old Angolan refugee

reunited in London with her 4-year-old adoptive daughter. The woman believed that an evil spirit had possessed her adoptive daughter as she claimed that the child was having nightmares, sleepwalking during the night, and speaking with people who were not present in the room. Although, the biological mother's sister did not notice any of these 'symptoms' while taking care of the child. The child's adoptive mother believed that the family of the deceased biological mother sent potent and dangerous spirits that possessed the child. Therefore, the adoptive mother decided to return to Angola with the baby to set her free from the evil spirits through a ceremony. However, the local social services went to court to prevent the return of the child to Angola and referred the case to Littlewood as a clinical psychiatrist who helped the child get a proper diagnosis (Littlewood, 2004).

In the delusional mind of the perpetrators, they have never abused the victims but just attempted to save them; therefore, the violence to which the victim will be subject is directed at the demon or the evil entity and not at the child (Carta et al., 2005). Based on Pierre (2023) it is a fact that 40-50% of the population believes in possession, some "evidence" suggests that cases are increasing. A proper medical diagnosis of possession can unveil different possibilities between what is real and what could be considered delusional as it is common for people with psychotic disorders to engage with the delusional belief that the devil or demons possess them. Moreover, identifying the most common triggers of possession experiences could be the key to getting the right help (Pierre, 2023). An example is the case of a child who died from asphyxiation at a Pentecostal church in San Jose, California. Her mother, uncle, and grandfather tried to expel what they believed was an "evil spirit," as reported by the authorities (Traub, 2022). Furthermore, Pierre (2023), Psychiatry has often defined the possession experience as a "ritualized trance state" or "dissociation" with the potential overlap between the two altered states of consciousness. Brendan Maher, a Harvard psychologist, insists on the theory that delusional beliefs are merely reasonable explanations for "anomalous experiences" (Pierre, 2023). Also, the medical literature insists on the biological component of the possession conditions, for instance, in the case of Anneliese Michael, who was an epileptic subject; in another case (further pieces of information are not disclosed), the medical literature explained how the case of possession was possible to be clarified by evidence of structural abnormality in the patient's part of the brain called basal ganglia in association with lack of blood flow to his temporal lobe (Pierre, 2023).

3.4 Clinical Diagnosis & Treatment

Harris (1957) pointed out that possession is a concept commonly used when misidentifying illnesses like epilepsy and other psychiatric conditions. Based on Copin & Bibeau (1980), Clinicians also pointed out that there is a significant link between psychiatric issues like depression, which frequently is the

reason behind the unusual behaviours associated with what faith/belief-oriented individuals name 'possession'. Moreover, schizophrenia is often confused with possession even if the pattern associated with it is consistently more idiosyncratic and less standardised by culture (Copin & Bibeau, 1980).

Following the definition provided by the Association of Maternal & Child Health Programs (AMCHP), cultural brokers are trained people who can establish a trustful relationship between groups or persons from unfamiliar cultural backgrounds. The figure of the cultural broker is an intermediary whose aims are to help people access the health system, education, or human services system (AMCHP, 2023). Therefore, Littlewood (2004) insists on the importance of understanding the local culture and emphasizes the danger of disregarding that culture which can lead to negative outcomes like losing the patient or ignoring the patient's interpretation, hence failing to prevent a recurrence.

Chapter 4: Conclusion

In conclusion, it is possible to say that based on Clarck et al. (2023) child abuse linked to faith or belief (CALFB) is a here in the UK. The negative outcomes of this abuse can have short-term and long-term consequences on the victims (Clarck et al., 2023). The Metropolitan Police (2023) was able to investigate and charge distinct types of abuse linked to faith or belief. Specifically, CALFB is a very under-researched area based on the data provided by the Metropolitan Police in 2023 (Met Police, 2023). Moreover, according to data collected by the review conducted in 2006 by CWRC, only a small minority of people with such beliefs abuse children. Therefore, it is possible to consider this abuse rare and peculiar to certain situations and dynamics (GOV.UK 2023). It urges improving the data collection and the information about the prevalence of this phenomenon as most of the data is now old and obsolete and not explicative of current situations.

Stobart (2006) described the abusers as usually poor people who are escaping from traumatic situations, who arrived in the UK and struggle with finding a job and learning the language; Based on the review conducted by Stobart in 2006, the data suggested that the potential victims of abuse linked to faith or belief are vulnerable children who are singled out as 'peculiar' or 'different', hence children with learning disabilities, mental issues, or behavioural issues (Stobart, 2006). Based on the Government this includes the belief in witchcraft or spirit possession, present mostly in many cultures like for example the devil for the catholic church, the evil eye, or djinns in the Islamic culture, and dakini in the Hindu culture (GOV.UK, 2023).

Since 2009, the Centre for Family Involvement (VCU) has trained and employed cultural brokers to help the cultural mediation in specific situations like when children are abused in connection with faith or belief with the Black, African American, Arabic, Asian, Latino, and refugee and immigrant communities (AMCHP, 2023). For example, AFRUCA and City and Hackney Safeguarding Children Partnership will deliver free, comprehensive full-day training in November 2024, January, and February 2025 to faith leaders, workers, and volunteers in local Black and African churches, mosques, Anglican, Catholic Churches and other places of worship across Hackney. The workshop will help the participants to understand how to assess the risks of harm to children in the faith setting. Participants will also understand their role and responsibility in keeping children safe outside faith settings (AFRUCA, 2024). However, most of the time, social workers can support the biological approach and dismiss the family's cultural practices of the child involved. Therefore, Littlewood (2004) insists on the importance of

understanding different cultures and belief systems; criminalizing them will can make people afraid of the institutions and vulnerable children more easily exposed to various kinds of abuse and exploitation (Littlewood, 2004). Both Metropolitan Police and charities are trying their best to tackle CALFB and spread awareness regarding a niche phenomenon in the UK, which is common in different religions and systems of belief. Furthermore, it is identifying the complicated relationship between mental illness and religion (Littlewood, 2004).

This research is an attempt to increase awareness about CALFB; as a main recommendation, I must highlight the necessity of a better understanding of the phenomenon of CALFB in depth as protecting all children from any abuse and exploitation should be a main priority for all societies and cultures. Also, The Victoria Climbié Foundation UK (2024) insists on the necessity of increasingly overlooked strategic and statutory approaches to address related harm as there is a risk of only focusing on certain faith settings, where children are routinely accused of being possessed. Moreover, community involvement is an essential factor in child protection as victims will continue to be silently missed or remain unsupported within child safeguarding processes; including migrant children in non-faith settings, as well as those arriving unaccompanied or being trafficked to the UK (vcf-uk.org, 2024). Moreover, improving communication with the NHS will also be fundamental in the prevention of harm to people/children with mental illness or learning disabilities.

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